

The Origins of the High-Z Supernova Search Team and the Discovery of the Accelerating Universe

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The National Optical Astronomy Observatory (NOAO), and specifically its southern hemisphere facility the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO), now both part of NSF's NOIRLab, played a key role in the discovery of the accelerating Universe. On the occasion of the 25th anniversary of the publications that announced this unexpected finding, we discuss the role our High-z Supernova Search Team and CTIO played in this startling discovery.

In 1986, the nearest supernova discovered since 1972 (SN 1986G), which fell into the then newly designated Type Ia class, appeared in Centaurus A. It was a time of peak *Hubble* Constant controversy, with camps polarized between values of $H_0=50$ and 100 km/s/Mpc. Work in 1984 and 1985 separated the type I class of supernovae in two, with one class clearly resulting from the demise of stripped massive stars (SN Ib/Ic) and the other, SN Ia, presumed to be some form of Chandrasekhar mass thermonuclear detonation of a white dwarf. Quality data were sparse, but were consistent with SN Ia being a highly uniform group of objects that held great promise for measuring accurate distances over cosmologically large scales.

Mark Phillips led a program to observe SN 1986G from CTIO, with spectra and photometry from the optical through IR. It was one of the first digital datasets, using state-of-the-art equipment that had recently been deployed at CTIO. SN 1986G was highly obscured by dust. There wasn't that much to compare it to, but Brian remembers Mark telling him that it did seem odd relative to what a SN Ia was supposed to be. This observing campaign was the beginning of CTIO's major role in producing and analyzing the digital datasets that underpin modern supernova studies.

In 1990, Brian travelled with his PhD supervisor, Bob Kirshner (later Adam's as well), to Les Houches to attend a five-week supernova workshop. There, they met Mario Hamuy, who was working at CTIO as a research assistant for CTIO astronomer Nick Suntzeff. Mario was well known for the photometric data that he and Nick had amassed on SN 1987A in the Large Magellanic Cloud.

Mario told the workshop of a new project, the Calán/Tololo Supernova Survey, which would use the Curtis Schmidt

telescope at CTIO to discover objects at redshifts more distant than the objects we were all studying. By discovering SN at $0.02 < z < 0.1$, the Calán/Tololo survey aimed to rigorously test SN Ia as standard candles, using the redshift as an accurate proxy for relative distance. The members of this group — Mario, Nick, and Mark at CTIO, and José Maza at the University of Chile — were starting their program that year.

When Brian visited CTIO in 1991 to work with the group on his thesis for a month, the Calán/Tololo survey was well underway. A few days after arrival, Mario showed off some of his first couple of objects. One of them, SN 1990af, looked pretty normal with respect to its spectrum, but compared to the average Leibundgut SN Ia template, it clearly rose and fell more quickly. More significantly, SN 1990af was fainter than the other objects, despite being at the same redshift. Mario was a bit depressed, because he felt that the Calán/Tololo program to use SN Ia to measure H_0 might be a dead end. But 1991 was a transformational year for SN Ia, being the year that 1991bg (faint, fast-evolving) and SN 1991T (bright, slow-evolving) appeared, which made it clear that SN Ia were definitely not identical photometrically or spectroscopically.

In 1993, based on the range of objects being studied in the nearby universe including SN 1991T and SN 1991bg, and consistent with the picture that was emerging from the Calán/

Figure 1: Our first proposal to measure q_0

Tololo survey, Mark Phillips wrote his seminal paper that compared the amount that a SNIa faded over 15 days after peak (Δm_{15}) to its luminosity, finding that faster-falling objects were systematically fainter than their slower-falling counterparts. Adam, then a first-year graduate student working with Bob Kirshner and Bill Press, began a monitoring campaign at the Fred Lawrence Whipple Observatory to classify SN reports and collect SN Ia light curves in the North, the Center for Astrophysics (CfA) I sample (1993–1996), while developing a method to correlate the whole SN Ia light curve shape with luminosity.

In 1994, Mario visited Harvard where Brian was now a postdoc and Adam a second-year graduate student. Using the Δm_{15} relation on the completely independent Calán/Tololo dataset, he showed us that the scatter of the SN Ia distances around the *Hubble* line was 7% — a massive improvement on any other distance measure at the time that could probe the *Hubble* flow. This dataset (29 SN Ia) and the CfA I sample (22 SN Ia) underpinned Adam’s development of his Multi Light Curve Shape (MLCS) method for SN Ia distances, which also combined corrections for the Phillips relation with color corrections to account for reddening by dust. In March of 1994, Saul Perlmutter of the Supernova Cosmology Project (SCP) enlisted the help of Bob, Adam, and Peter Challis on an observing run at the MMT to classify the highest redshift SN Ia yet observed at that time, SN 1994G at $z=0.425$ (IAUC 5956), which the SCP discovered at Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO), NOAO’s northern-hemisphere facility.

In mid-1994, Brian once again returned to CTIO for an unrelated observing program on the 1.5m telescope. Based on the accuracy of SN Ia distances from the CTIO and CfA work, and the demonstration by the SCP and collaborators that SN Ia could be discovered and classified, he and Nick hatched a plan to use the CTIO 4m (named the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope in 1995) to extend the approach of the Calán/Tololo survey to $z > 0.3$ while adding digital image subtraction methods. The advantage of the CTIO 4m is it had an extremely good $2k \times 2k$ imager (covering $15' \times 15'$) at a site that offered 95% clear weather for parts of the year. The High-Z team was formed in the second half of 1994, and our first proposal was submitted on 29 September 1994.

Brian moved to Australia at the end of 1994 and began developing a data reduction pipeline to process SN-search images. As we started to implement the pipeline at CTIO, it became clear we had a problem or two. The CTIO computing system had substantial differences from the system Brian was using in Australia, which prevented the software from

running. To confound matters, the internet connection between Australia and Chile was about 1 character per second.

Our first observations were taken on 25 February 1995, and we had another night’s data on 06 March. The processing of this data was an unmitigated disaster—nothing seemed to work, and Brian could not get the data to Australia to diagnose what was going wrong. We resorted to emailing tiny 16×16 pixel stamps of interesting things to Australia (the only method at the time to get data across the slow connection). These little mini images, combined with as vivid descriptions as could be mustered by telephone, were the basis of the entire team at CTIO working together to slowly fix the pipeline.

Figure 2: Object C14 – actual finding chart (complete with typo)

We had two more nights on 24 and 29 March 1995, while having a proposal to write for a continuation of our program due on 30 March. Around 27 March, the pipeline started to produce interesting objects, and searching the data from 29 March, we discovered a single object, C14, later named SN 1995K, that got everyone excited. It was a new object, buried in a spiral galaxy. It didn’t move, and it appeared to be possibly fainter in our poor data from 24 March.

Using the CTIO 4m spectrograph, Mark was able to obtain a spectrum of the galaxy — it was at a redshift of $z = 0.48$ — making it potentially the most distant SN yet detected. This was followed up with confirmation of it being a SN Ia at ESO a few days later by Bruno Leibundgut and Jason Spyromilio.

For the next five years, twice a year, we would converge in Chile (and starting in 1997, in Hawai’i to use the Canada France Hawaii Telescope 4m) to use the CTIO 4m Blanco

telescope to find supernovae, which would then be classified and followed-up with telescopes across Chile, and in Hawai'i (including Alex Filippenko, his group, and Adam at Keck). The Blanco imager was upgraded to the BTC (Big Throughput Camera) through the efforts of Tony Tyson and colleagues, and the CTIO 4m telescope remained the workhorse of both the High-Z and SCP teams. Group members of both High-Z

and SCP passed each other at airports and observatory control rooms like ships in the night.

Only in 1996 did we apply to use the KPNO 4m telescope, which we were rejected for in favor of the SCP. Informal feedback to Brian from a member of the KPNO Time Allocation Committee (TAC) at the time was the complaint that SCP had seven objects consistent with $\Omega_M \sim 1$, while we had only one. And while ours had the smallest uncertainty, it was deeply in negative q_0 territory — feedback indicated that the TAC didn't think we had our act together. While Brian was not very unhappy at the time with that feedback — we dodged a bullet. The importance of consistent clear weather with good seeing cannot be understated. When discoveries require two epochs to be made, success is proportional to $P(\text{good weather})^2$. For CTIO $P \sim 95\%$ compared to KPNO where $P \sim 60\%$, a huge difference for the success of our project. The High-Z team simply did not have the human power to discover SN at both KPNO and CTIO simultaneously and could not afford following up a search run that only had a 1/3 chance of success.

Figure 3: The top panel shows a *Hubble*-diagram of SN Ia photometrically-estimated distance moduli as a function of redshift, with the predictions from three different cosmological models shown. The bottom panel shows the residuals from the $\Omega_M = 0.2, \Omega_\Lambda = 0.0$ model, which had been the observationally favored cosmological model at the time. The high-redshift SN are markedly fainter than expected. With the $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$ model, which implies accelerating expansion over the redshift interval shown, the data are now explained. *Figure from Riess et al. (1998).*

Each observing run was organized chaos. Brian would arrive a week before observations were scheduled, with the latest version of the software. Since we did not have dedicated equipment, the whole pipeline would be re-built at the beginning of each run. Due to the size of our dataset, we needed to operate across essentially all available machines and disks of the observatory — and this was hardware that changed with each run. The week inevitably ended with the entire team working 20-hour days to ensure that we were able to promptly discover supernovae. Probably the best sense of an observing run was captured in the 2000 PBS documentary, “Runaway Universe.” Adding to the stress was a hard deadline set by the Space Telescope Science Institute (STScI) to provide targets for our nascent *Hubble Space Telescope (HST)* Program. A slot in the *Hubble* schedule was held for us within a ~ 1 degree search radius, with final coordinates to be provided on the first Tuesday by noon following the search. At the time, *HST* was so new that failing to find a target, and shooting blank sky, was unthinkable.

Despite the chaos, through 1995 to 1997, we did manage to discover, spectroscopically confirm, and photometrically

follow 16 distant SN Ia — enough to, in theory, make a statistically robust measurement of the deceleration parameter.

But analysis of high-redshift SN Ia data was not straightforward. Undertaking the K-corrections to convert the redshifted data to a common frame was hard, and here, CTIO led the way. Accurate K-corrections require accurate understanding of bandpasses and accurate spectrophotometry of SN Ia as they evolve. Nick and Mario went through the process of re-observing spectrophotometric standards with the new instrumentation to provide higher quality standards. This spectrophotometry was used by the CTIO group, the High-Z team, and people around the world to improve the quality of spectrophotometry of SN Ia, and it was also a key ingredient to understand the bandpasses we were using to calculate the K-corrections. Likewise, the use of SN colors to account for extinction was a tricky task, with the team using an early-for-the-day Bayesian formalism developed by Adam in MLCS to infer extinction from colors. An initial analysis from just 4 SNe Ia led by Peter Garnavich in late 1997/early 1998 reached a landmark conclusion that the Universe was at least not strongly decelerating ($\Omega_M < 1$).

Adam then led the analysis of the full sample. When the calibrated photometry was in, Adam's MLCS and the Mark Phillip's Δm_{15} were used to derive the light curve shape corrections, which along with the redshifts, color-based extinction measures, K-corrections, and the local sample of SNe from Calán-Tololo and CfA I, provided the foundational ingredients to making the cosmological measurements. The initial analysis perplexed Adam, who couldn't understand why the data preferred a negative value for Omega matter (without the option of a Cosmological constant offered). Further analysis found, no matter what we did, that the Universe was accelerating with > 99.9% confidence. It was not easy for the team to come to terms with such an outlandish proposition. Our strongest test against our biggest concern, SN Ia evolution, was our finding that local SN Ia distances were consistent (i.e., same expansion rate) between old, elliptical hosts and young spirals.

Ultimately we agreed that it was what the data showed, and we needed to publish. We submitted "Observational Evidence for an Accelerating Universe and a Cosmological Constant" to *The Astronomical Journal* on 13 March 1998 (accepted 06 May),

a paper which is now the most cited science paper in the field of astronomy and astrophysics (as of last check, over 23,000 citations to date). The fact that the SCP arrived at the same answer independently and in the same time frame made the broader acceptance perhaps a bit easier and faster than most of us expected.

The High-Z SN Search team's discovery of the accelerating Universe was founded with people and instrumentation of CTIO. Twenty-five years on, despite better understanding of dust and the diversity of SN Ia, the data collected largely at CTIO in the 1990s that led to the discovery of the accelerating Universe have held up to a dramatic increase in scale and ever-improving instrumentation. It also marked the start of an important transition where NOAO started supporting large-scale projects, rather than just individual small-N investigator-lead programs. That transition continues apace, leaving many of us feeling nostalgic for the days of the past. But such is the progress of astronomy!

Figure 4: The evidence for dark energy, just using SN Ia alone, has gotten tremendously stronger with each passing year since 1998. This figure shows the recent cosmological parameter constraints provided by the "Pantheon" SN sample of Scolnic et al. (2018). The outer black contours show the original 68% and 85% confidence-interval constraints provided by Riess et al. (1998)